

KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF CRIMINAL ABORTION AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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Knowledge and attitude of criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Abstract: *The study investigated the influence of knowledge and attitude of criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The study utilized the ex-post factor research design. It is a descriptive research design in which relevant data are collected by the use of questionnaire to elicit responses from respondents. The target population of the study comprised all 4200 level 200 and 300 education students in the tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom States. A sample size of three hundred (300) students was selected for the study using purposive sampling technique. The researcher-developed instrument “Knowledge and Attitude of Criminal Abortion among Female Undergraduate Students in Tertiary institutions Questionnaire” (KACAFUSTIQ) was used to collect data for this study. Face validity was employed in this study. The reliability of the instrument will be established by administering the instrument “Knowledge and Attitude of Criminal Abortion among Female Undergraduate Students in Tertiary institutions Questionnaire” (KACAFUSTIQ)” on 30 students who were not part of the main study. The scores obtained from this pilot group were subjected to a test of internal consistency using the Cronbach’s alpha reliability analysis and the overall reliability of study stood at 0.87 which was deemed adequate for the study. Data generated from the instrument was analyzed using linear regression analysis. The result obtained from the data analysis indicated that there is a significant influence of knowledge and attitude of criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The study recommended that proper knowledge on the consequences associated with criminal abortion should be transfer to the students as this will help to prevent them from involvement in criminal abortion. There is also a need for early sex education from parents as this can influence abortion perception and practice in later years.*

Introduction

The impact of criminal abortion on female undergraduates has been receiving a great deal of attention in the society especially among health

professionals. Abortion is the termination of a pregnancy by removal or expulsion of an embryo or fetus. Criminal abortions are unlawful abortions carried by women with unwanted

pregnancy. It has to do with the interruption of pregnancy by the mother herself or another person for freedom. Criminal abortions is an abortion that does not conform to statutory provisions governing the performance of abortions. It is a crime to destroy embryo life after gestation has begun. According to Okagbue, (2019), criminal abortion are illegal action performed to be save by woman during conceivment of unplanned pregnancy It is an abortion that has been viewed as the termination of pregnancy before the age of viability (28 weeks of gestation). It is a practice that has to do with the expulsion or extraction of a foetus or an embryo weighing 500 grams or less from its mother (Ononokpono *et al*, 2020). The abortion are quite common, and because they are often performed clandestinely or by unskilled medical providers are most are unsafe.

The term “criminal abortion” is common among women despite its effects such as physical, psychological and physiological effects. The involvement in criminal abortion by students pose major health risks to women in the reproductive age group. Female undergraduates are particularly exposed to these risks due to knowledge and attitude toward involvement illicit sexual activity. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2023) defined criminal abortion as a procedure for terminating an unwanted pregnancy, either by a person lacking the necessary skill or in an environment lacking the minimum standard or both. This criminal act by students causes a huge threat and burden to women’s reproductive health most especially in countries where it is illegal. About 210 million

pregnancies occur every year all over the world, 80 million are unwanted, 46 million end in induced abortion and nearly 20 million are estimated to be unsafe resulting in the death of 80,000 women annually and 95% of these deaths occur in developing countries. Of these unsafe abortions, the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023) reported that about 5.3 million women suffer disabilities. It has been estimated that 97% of criminal abortion occurs in developing countries. The annual hospitalization rate for complications of abortion is 4-7 percent. Engagement in criminal abortion by students has serious health risks, which sometime leads to death to young girls. The involvement of the unsafe abortion also results in various complications such as haemorrhage, perforation of the uterus, secondary sterify and even death. Major *et al* (2023) reported that the psychological effects of criminal abortion is associated with negative emotions which may increased after abortion. It is also associated with depression, decreased in self-esteem and development of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD). The risks of criminal abortion include infection, excessive bleeding, damage to the uterus, or adverse reactions to anesthesia (Onukwugha *et al.*, 2020). Criminal abortion especially when unsafe can endanger a woman’s reproductive health and lead to serious life-threatening complications and even death. Symptoms of unsafe abortion can vary depending on various factors such as the stage of pregnancy, methods used, and overall health condition. Some common symptoms may include severe abdominal pain, heavy bleeding

or hemorrhage, fever, weakness, dizziness, fainting spells, and even signs of infection.

The most common complications reported by women hospitalized due to criminal abortion include excessive pain, bleeding and fever (Fasubaa and Ezechi, 2023). According to Fasubaa and Ezechi (2023) women who had unsafe abortions are mostly treated for retained products of conception, haemorrhage, fever, sepsis and instrumental injury. It may be difficult to ascertain the statistics of maternal mortality due to criminal abortion in Nigeria. However, the Society of Gynaecologist and Obstetrician of Nigeria and Henshaw and colleagues revealed that about 3000 women die from complications of unsafe abortions each year.(Ubajaka, *et al*, 2022). More than half of these women were adolescents. Criminal abortions mostly put the life and health of any woman in jeopardy. According to Igbolekwu *et al* (2019), many students involved in criminal abortion as an alternative to their perceived consequences of the unwanted pregnancy such as school dropout, societal shame, education disruption and emotional disgrace. Criminal abortions often occur where abortion is illegally carried out.

Most unsafe abortions occur where modern birth control is unavailable, or in developing countries where affordable and well-trained medical practitioners are not readily available. According to Adeola (2022), age, personal interest, family economic status, level of education, religion, residence and family status of the students significantly influenced the practice of criminal abortion. Most undergraduate students resort to criminal abortion due to a lack of safe options

and unbearable pregnancies. Legal limitations, moral judgment, and stigma can inhibit access to safe abortion care. Several factors are reported to be responsible for unsafe abortion practice, including some of the following: place of residence, knowledge of pregnancy signs and symptoms, being a student and age during pregnancy (Balogun, 2020). It also include delay after the decision for abortion, religious stigma, sexual assault, financial problems, and a lack of understanding or clarity about what the law allows. Other factors may includes students knowledge and attitude to consequences associated with criminal abortion.

Knowledge about the consequences associated with criminal abortion is vital to undergraduate students. Knowledge play a pivotal role on students' practice of criminal abortion. Knowledge has to with the level of awareness of an individual. Knowledge is facts, information, and skills acquired through experience or education. The word knowledge has to do with the individuals' understanding and skills associated with criminal abortion. It is the process of being aware of the practice of criminal abortion. According to Abiola (2020), most undergraduate female students are aware of criminal abortion. Oke (2021) reported that nearly all female student of higher institutions practice criminal abortion on daily basis. When students are aware and also have knowledge about the consequences associated with criminal abortion, they stop engaging in the activity and see criminal abortion as illicit act with their attitude.

Bearak *et al*, (2020) reported that knowledge is very important when it comes to termination of unplanned pregnancies. According to Bearak *et al* (2020), most undergraduate students engaged in criminal abortion due to lack of knowledge of the consequences associated with it. Ban *et al.*, (2020) also reported that students at school terminate unplanned pregnancies for various reasons; these include lack of knowledge, fear of expulsion from school, unstable relationships, financial instability and lack of support from the partner Knowledge of criminal abortion by students is important because of its dire reproductive health consequences and impact on maternal morbidity and mortality. Most women in the university environment are away from home for the first time and become free to experiment sexually especially without any parental supervision. This act can lead to unplanned pregnancy that result in criminal abortion. According Abebe *et al*, (2022), most students have low level of knowledge of the consequences associated with criminal abortion. This low level of knowledge enable them to engage illicit sexual activity that result in engagement in criminal abortion.

Student attitude to criminal abortion has an issue of concern. Attitude is the way of thinking that affects individuals' behaviour. It is the feeling that students had about abortion. Attitude may be positive or negative. Positive deals with positive thinking while negative attitude deals with negative thinking concerning criminal abortions. According to Balogun (2022), there is generally a negative approach to issues of criminal abortion. Criminal abortion

are not spoken openly and comfortably within the school, as is often the case with other sexual topics (Sakar *et.al*, 2022). Social prohibitions and negative attitudes on discussing the consequences associated with criminal abortion clearly in the school organization prevent students from accessing accurate information as regard to criminal abortion (Pandit *et al*, 2024). Individuals' attitude to criminal abortion determines their reaction to these phenomena irrespective of age. Okon (2021) reported that level of sex education contribute effectively to criminal abortion. This is because most students are not properly fed with the right information concerning criminal abortion which reduces the level of awareness of the consequences of criminal abortion among students.

Bearak *et al*, (2020) reported that most students engaged in criminal abortion due to negative attitude to the complication associated with criminal abortion. The most effective way to prevent criminal abortion is the use of emergency contraception after involvement in unprotected sex. Ganatra *et al* (2017) Found that students' attitude to abortion is associated with factors. These factors associated with attitudes towards abortion include peer group, religious affiliation, religious attendance, educational experiences, circumstances of the pregnancy and political affiliation. Mothers' and friends' attitudes have also been associated with individual students' attitudes towards abortion. Studies have also found students with sexual experience are more likely to hold positive attitudes towards abortion than their counterparts with no sexual experience. Sexual

experience is a strong determinant of students' attitude to abortion and attitude is related to knowledge. Bain *et al* (2020) indicated that a positive relationship exist between knowledge and sex education either through knowing someone who has had an abortion, through formal education or sexuality education

Hindin and Fatusi (2019) reported that effective school-based sexuality education help to lower the rate of abortion among students. Masvawure (2018) posited that effective sex education teaches students about sexual intimacy, enlightens students on their reproductive systems, birth control, and sexually transmitted diseases. It also exposes students to their gender identity, gender role, family role, body images, sexual expression (what it entails and how to time it), intimacy and the marriage relationship. When proper sex education is carry out, it help to improve students knowledge on criminal abortion. According to Nwagugu *et al.*, (2018), high-quality sexuality education delivers positive health outcomes, with lifelong impacts. Effective sex education helps to protect students from unintended pregnancies and abortion. Sexuality education also helps them prepare for and manage physical and emotional changes as they grow up, including during puberty and adolescence, while teaching them about respect, consent and where to go if they need help. This in turn reduces risks from violence, exploitation and abuse. That is lack of sex education in schools is the major cause of abortion among secondary school girls. Sex education is a means of solving the problem of abortion which link

students with the level of awareness of the consequences associated with the act.

Awareness of the consequences associated with criminal abortion play a significant role among female undergraduate students. When students are aware of the consequences associated with criminal abortion, they likely reduce the rate of engagement in illicit sexual activity that will result in criminal abortion. Awareness of criminal abortion has to do with the understanding of criminal abortion. Chisaa *et al.*,(2020) reported that the level of awareness of students concerning abortion in Nigeria was low which increases the mortality resulting from abortion. According to Chisaa *et al.*,(2020) abortion mortality and morbidity tend to be higher when students have low knowledge of the consequences associated with criminal abortion. According to Arisukwu *et al* (2019), the level of awareness of criminal abortion among students is associated with students' age.

Age plays a significant role in students' engagement in criminal abortion. Age is the number of years an individual spend on earth. It has to do with the process of being young and old. The level of awareness of criminal abortion among undergraduate students based on age is a controversial issues. Most younger people at the university level that are more aware of criminal abortion and engaged in criminal abortion than older people (Yaya *et al* 2018). Criminal abortion is an important preventable cause of maternal deaths and morbidities. It can also lead to physical and mental health complications. This required creating good awareness to students. This awareness require the help of both parents

and teachers. It is expected that when both parents and teachers give proper sex education to students, it help to reduce the rate of criminal abortion among them. The Levels of unintended pregnancy and unsafe abortion continue to be high when there is no proper sex education (Dickson *et al*, 2018) Based on this background, the students intends to investigate the influence knowledge and attitude towards criminal abortion among Tertiary institutions female undergraduates.

Statement of the Problem

Criminal abortions are unlawful abortions which has to do with the interruption of pregnancy by the mother herself or another person. Criminal abortions mostly put the life and health of many women in jeopardy. The most common complications reported by women hospitalized due to criminal abortion include excessive pain, bleeding, severe abdominal pain, weakness, dizziness, fainting spells, and even signs of infection. This contributes to high morbidity and mortality rate. Despite the effects associated with criminal abortion. Over the years, there has been issues of criminal abortions especially among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions. The researcher worried of what could be the reasons behind criminal abortion among undergraduate students. The researcher suggest could it be due to students' lack of knowledge, and positive attitude to criminal abortion. Could students' age contribute to undergraduate students involvement in criminal abortion. It has been shown that undergraduate students are constantly exposed to unhealthy sexual behaviours and negative health effects

due to lack of sex education and access to sexual and reproductive health information. This becomes the central problem of the study.

The findings of this study would be of immense benefit to the following groups, students, health education officer, policy makers, ministry of health, lecturers, students and researchers. This study will serve as a lecture note to the lecturers who are the implementer of health education curriculum at the university level and also will help them to know the consequences associated with criminal abortion among students. The finding of the study would serve as an insight to the researcher who might consult it in the process of carrying out similar research in the future. The study would provide additional literature that could enrich the existing one in area of students' knowledge and attitude towards criminal abortion. Based on this background, the present study intends to investigate the influence knowledge and attitude towards criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Purpose of the Study

The principal objective of this study is to investigate knowledge and of criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study seek to:

1. Determine the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

2. Determine the attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State
3. Determine how sex education influence criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Research Questions

The following questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State?
3. What is the influence sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulate to guide the study.

1. There is no significant influence of the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State
2. There is no significant influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State.
3. There is no significant influence of sex education on criminal abortion among female

undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Research Method

The study utilized the ex-post factor research design. It is a descriptive research design in which relevant data are collected by the use of questionnaire to elicit responses from respondents. The target population of the study comprised all 4200 level 200 and 300 education students in the tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom States. A sample size of three hundred (300) students was selected for the study using purposive sampling technique. The researcher-developed instrument “Knowledge and Attitude of Criminal Abortion among Female Undergraduate Students in Tertiary institutions Questionnaire” (KACAFUSTIQ)” was used to collect data for this study. Face validity was employed in this study. The reliability of the instrument will be established by administering the instrument “Knowledge and Attitude of Criminal Abortion among Female Undergraduate Students in Tertiary institutions Questionnaire” (KACAFUSTIQ)” on 30 students who were not take part of the main study. The scores obtained from this pilot group were subjected to a test of internal consistency using the Cronbach’s alpha reliability analysis and the overall reliability of study stood at 0.87 which was deem adequate for the study. data generated from the instrument was analyzed using linear regression analysis.

Result

Research Question 1:What is the influence of level of knowledge on criminal abortion among

female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State?

Table1: Simple Linear Regression analysis of the influence of level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Model	R	R –Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.919	.844	.781	.25371

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 1 shows the value of regression analysis of the influence of level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The coefficient of prediction(R^2) is .844. This indicates that 84.4% of criminal abortion is attributed to level of education among female

undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Research Question 2: What is the influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression analysis of the influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Model	R	R -Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.898	.792	.785	.31630

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 2 shows the value of regression of analysis of the influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions Akwa Ibom State. The coefficient of prediction(R^2) is .792. This showed that 79.2% of criminal abortion is attributed to level of education among female undergraduate

students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Research Question 3: What is the influence sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions Akwa Ibom State?

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression analysis of the influence sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Model	R	R -Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.797	.635	.575	.38100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 3 shows the value of regression of analysis of the influence sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The coefficient of prediction (R^2) is .635. This showed that 63.5% of influence sex education on criminal

abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Table 4.: Simple Linear regression analysis of the influence of the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Source of Variable	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Remark
Regression	6101.652	1	6101.652	60.58	.000	Sig.
Residual	30115.437	299	100.72			
Total	36,217.089	300				

* = Significant at $P < .05$ alpha level, Source: Field survey (2025).

The result presented in Table 4. shows the simple linear regression analysis of influence of the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. This indicates that the F-value of 60.58 obtained at 1 and 299 degrees of freedom had an associated p-value of .000, which is less than 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is a significant influence of the level

of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 5: Simple Linear regression analysis of the influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Source of Variable	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Remark
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Regression	6100.913	1	6100.913	60.57	.000	Sig.
Residual	30116.176	299	100.72			
Total	36,217.089	300				

* = Significant at P<.05 alpha level, Source: Field survey (2025).

The result presented in Table 5 shows the simple linear regression analysis of the influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. This indicates that the F-value of 60.36 obtained at 1 and 299 degrees of freedom had an associated p-value of .000, which is less than 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the null

hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is no significant influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Research Hypothesis 3: There is no significant influence of sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Table 6: Simple Linear regression analysis of the influence of sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Source of Variable	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Remark
Regression	6009.115	1	6009.115	59.47	.001	Sig.
Residual	30207.974	299	101.03			
Total	36,217.089	300				

* = Significant at P<.05 alpha level, Source: Field survey (2025).

The result presented in Table shows the simple linear regression analysis of the influence of sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. This indicates that the F-value of 59.47 obtained at 1 and 299 degrees of freedom had an associated p-value of .001, which is less than 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is no significant influence of sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Findings of the study

The findings obtained from the study are as follows:

1. Level of knowledge influence criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State
2. Attitude influence criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State
3. Sex education influence criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State
4. There is significant influence of the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among

female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

5. There is significant influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State
6. There is significant influence of sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State

Discussion of Findings

The result presented in Table 1 indicated that level of knowledge influence criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The hypothesis presented in Table 4 indicated that there is significant influence of the level of knowledge on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions Akwa Ibom State. This finding may be due to the fact that the level of knowledge of undergraduate students can determine their involvement in criminal abortion. This finding is in line with the finding of Bearak *et al* (2020) who reported that knowledge is very important when it comes to termination of unplanned pregnancies. Bearak *et al* (2020) reported that most students engage in criminal abortion due to lack of knowledge of the consequences associated with it. Ban *et al.*, (2020) also reported that peoples at school terminate unplanned pregnancies for various reasons; these include lack of knowledge, fear of expulsion from school, unstable relationships, financial instability and lack of support from the partner Knowledge of criminal abortion by students is important because of its dire

reproductive health consequences and impact on maternal morbidity and mortality. Most women in the university environment are away from home for the first time and become free to experiment sexually especially without any parental supervision. This act can lead to unplanned pregnancy that result in criminal abortion. According Abebe *et al*, (2022), most students have low level of knowledge of the consequences associated with criminal abortion. This low level of knowledge enable them to engage illicit sexual activity that result in engagement in criminal abortion.

The result presented in Table 2 showed that attitude influence criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The corresponding hypothesis in Table 5 showed that there is significant influence of attitude on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. This is in line with the finding of Bearak *et al* (2020) who reported that most students engage in criminal abortion due to negative attitude to the complication associated criminal abortion. The most effective way to prevent criminal abortion is the use of emergency contraception after involvement in unprotected sex. Ganatra *et al* (2017) Found that students' attitude to abortion is associated with factors. These factors associated with attitudes towards abortion include peer group, religious affiliation, religious attendance, educational experiences, circumstances of the pregnancy and political affiliation. Mothers' and friends' attitudes have also been associated with individual students' attitudes towards abortion. Studies have also found students with sexual experience are more likely to hold positive attitudes towards abortion than their

counterparts with no sexual experience. Sexual experience is a strong determinant of students' attitude to abortion and attitude is related to knowledge. Bain *et al* (2020). Indicated that a positive relationship exist between knowledge, either through knowing someone who has had an abortion or through formal education.

The result presented in Table 3 indicated sex education influence criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The corresponding hypothesis in Table 6 indicated that there is significant influence of sex education on criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State This finding in line with the finding of Hindin and Fatusi (2019) who reported that effective school-based sexuality education help to lower the rate of abortion among students. Masvawure (2018) effective sex education teaches students about sexual intimacy, enlightens students on their reproductive systems, birth control, and sexually transmitted diseases. It also exposes students to their gender identity, gender role, family role, body images, sexual expression (what it entails and how to time it), intimacy and the marriage relationship. When proper sex education are carry out, it help to improve students knowledge on criminal abortion. According to Nwagugu *et al.*, (2018), high-quality sexuality education delivers positive health outcomes, with lifelong impacts. Effective sex education helps to protect students from unintended pregnancies and abortion. Sexuality education also helps them prepare for and manage physical and emotional changes as they grow up, including during

puberty and adolescence, while teaching them about respect, consent and where to go if they need help. This in turn reduces risks from violence, exploitation and abuse. That is lack of sex education in schools is the major cause of abortion among secondary school girls. Sex education is a means of solving the problem of abortion which link students with consequences associated with the act.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the level of knowledge, attitude and sexuality education influence students' involvement in criminal abortion among female undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. It is also concluded that lack of knowledge, negative attitude and lack of sexuality education by either teachers or parents are strong determinant of students' involvement in criminal abortion. The prevalence of abortion is high and complicated by high morbidity rate despite the consequences associated with criminal abortion.

Recommendations

The following recommendation were made based on the findings of the study.

1. Proper knowledge on the consequences associated with criminal abortion should be transfer to the students as this will prevent them from involvement in criminal abortion.
2. Effective sex education should be given to students to enable them know the risk associated with criminal abortions.
3. Students should develop attitude that will work against criminal abortions.

4. Awareness should be created on the impact of criminal abortion on female undergraduate students.
5. There is a need for early sex education from parents as this can influence abortion perception and practice in later years.

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